

<p>Mood Disorder and Social Adjustment Among Senior Secondary School Students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria</p>		<p>Educational Psychology</p> <p>Keywords: Mood disorder, Social adjustment, etc.</p>
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Abstract

The study examined mood disorder and social adjustment among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State - Nigeria. The ex-post facto design was used. The population comprised senior secondary school students in both Calabar Municipal and Calabar South Local Government Areas respectively. The stratified random sampling technique was used. A total of seven hundred (700) subjects (364 males and 336 females) were selected from six (6) public secondary schools for the study. Data was obtained through a well-structured and validated questionnaire captioned Mood Disorder and Social Adjustment Scale (MDSAQ). Data collected were analyzed using population t-test and Linear Regression Analysis tested at .05 level of significance. The result of the analysis showed that mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is significantly high and the mood disorder also predicted their social adjustment. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that parents should create more positive mutual social atmosphere in the home to prevent mood disorder and enhance proper social adjustment of their ward.

Introduction

Children and adolescents are frequently referred to psychiatric consultation due to mood complaints. Over the last decades, there has been an increase in the recognition of mood disorders among young individuals, a reflection of the adoption of a developmental perspective to psychopathology. Longitudinal studies clearly indicate that mood disorders begin early in life, with the majority of first episodes occurring before adulthood (Kim-Cohen, Caspi, Moffitt, Harrington, Milne & Poulton, 2003).

Humans are bound to experience changes in their mood, sometimes we feel energetic loaded with ideas or suddenly irritated, sad or down casted. These moods remain so for adolescents and infused into adolescents’ daily routine or activities. The need for adolescents to fit into their daily routines despite the mood forms the crux of this study. The stage of critical maturation and development is the adolescence period. It is a transition from childhood to adulthood with age bracket from 11–20. Hence, emotional imbalances seem to be predominant, making them vulnerable to all forms of mood disorder. This emotional irritability arises from the inability to strike a balance between self – confidence and self– identity. This has lead to a feeling of intense sadness, helplessness, hopelessness and prevents their functionality. Observation shows that secondary school students in Calabar metropolis does not adjust well in school and this is evidenced by the way they relate with their peers, teachers and significant others. Many of them are withdraw, very irritable and unable to manage their emotion.

Despite all the effort that the Cross River State Government had done by providing schools with guidance and counselling services to address issues of mood disorder and poor social adjustment to give students a sense of direction. Yet, the level of mood disorder and poor adjustment among adolescents remains very relatively high. Hence, this study seeks to examine if mood disorder can be a factor in explaining poor social adjustment among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.

Purpose of the study

Specially, the study sought to determine:

1. To assess the extent to which mood disorder exists among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.
2. To find out if mood disorder predicts social adjustment among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.

Research questions

1. To what extent does mood disorder exist among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State?
2. Does mood disorder predict social adjustment among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State?

Research hypotheses

1. Mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is not significantly high.
2. Mood disorder does not significantly predict social adjustment among senior secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

Literature Review

Nairne (2000) defined mood disorder as prolonged and disabling disruptions in emotional state which comes in two main varieties: depressive disorders in which the person suffers from depression and bipolar disorders, which are characterized by mood swings between extreme heights called manic states and low depression. Latch (2015) sees mood disorder as selflessness of personal weakness, character flaws and poor parenting style. He further stressed that students who are depressed don't feel comfortable confiding in anyone because they feel nobody understands the experience they are going through and may not be able to proffer solutions to them. According to Krans (2015), mood disorder is characterized by periods of depression, sometimes alternating with periods of elevated mood. These disorders are associated with imbalances in chemicals that carry signals between brain cells (neurotransmitters).

Allen and Badcock (2003) indicated that depression is seen as a psychic hibernation; it slows down, defuses aggression and restrains risk taking. It begins at a tender stage accumulating to a point where the individual begins to hear strange voices and sudden suspiciousness which leads to schizophrenia. A study conducted by Adewuya and Ologun (2005) revealed that mood swings results from certain factors which includes depressive symptoms, adolescents' perceptions of family functioning, drug and substance abuse, inferiority complex and probably large family size. One of its consequences is its capable of disrupting the peace of the home which is evident in broken relationships as well as lead to deterioration in the adolescence performance academically.

Furthermore, in terms of sex differences pertaining to mood disorders, Wodker and Cettwafet (2014) in a study aimed at measuring the extent mood swings is prevalent among boys and girls. The results revealed that there is no significant difference in mood disorder but showed a positive and negative co-relationship between depression for girls and boys. Various studies by research scholars have identified the presence of mood swings among secondary school students. Harpes and Daane (1998) suggested that mood disorder affects affective, psychomotor and cognitive domain of learning while Sloan (2002) sees mood disorder as a construct that is related to lack of confidence, poor learning behaviours, low self efficacy and feeling of inadequacy. When mood disorder is recognized early, it helps them to adjust better, improve mood and function better in life as well as at school. It is important that teachers, administrators and other school staff should be knowledgeable about mood disorder as this can impair academic and interpersonal behaviour at school (Hammenn & Rudolph, 2003).

Ugodulunwa and Anakwe (2012) described social adjustment as a way in which an individual tries to deal with stress, conflict, tension and meet his or her needs while making efforts at the same time to maintain harmonious relationships with the environment. Adeyemo (2005:3) further stressed that social adjustment is the ability to cope, manage emotions and behave in socially appropriate and responsible way to meet with challenges and responsibilities. This means that in order to meet the social demands of the environment, one must develop coping ability of physiological and emotional components. Mizelle (1999) viewed that students' level of social adjustment as a phenomenal that forms the prerequisite for educationists as well as health practitioners. A study conducted by Kiuru, Nurmi, Aunola and Salmela (2009) on the influence of peer relations on all forms of adjustment among 1494 adolescents. He observed that 36 peer groups were formed. Result showed that members of adolescent peer groups resembled each other in terms of social adjustments and their ability to form clique based on their family background, parent socio-economic status among others.

Studies have shown that there is a high rate of depression among girls than among boys. Girls are 2 to 3 times more likely than men to develop consistent mood swings. For instance, boys are more likely to be irritable, angry and discouraged when depressed whereas women express "classical" symptoms of feeling worthlessness, helplessness, seeking for consolation at any given chance making vulnerable to any form of harassment as well as sad moods (Canadian Community Health Survey (CCHS), 2002).

The World Health Organization (2004) reports depressive disorders as one of the leading causes of disability for persons between ages 12 – 22. They established the adverse effects that depressed mood have on self-reported GPA in English, Mathematics, Arts and Science.

In a study conducted by Sawyer (2000) on the effect of family related variables on dissociative disorders among adolescents, 12 percent of adolescents reported symptoms of mood disorders while most hid it from their parents; almost 90 percent of their parents perceived their depressed teens as not suffering depression while others prefer speaking to their grandparents who are many more years of being at risk. It is imperative that the increase appears partly authentic but reflects adolescents' willingness to disclose their depressive state as well as the tendency to forget many negative experiences over time.

Darvern (2004) conducted a study to examine the relationship between depression and adjustment among third grade high school students. The result showed that students suffering from depression often experience social difficulties and problems maintaining friendship as a result of mood swings and their tendency to perceive relationships and interactions negatively.

Researchers have found positive associations between mood fluctuations, social adjustment, a highly significant correlation with tobacco use and alcohol consumption (Eccles, Barber, Stone & Hunt, 2003; Harrison & Narayan, 2003; Melnick, Miller, Sabo, Farrell, & Barnes, 2001) among adolescents and young adults. Fredriken, Keith, Reddy and Way (2004) examined the effect of diminished sleep on groups among Illinois middle school students. It was observed that insufficient sleep can reduce self esteem and academic performance which leads to bipolar depression hence depression is an endogenous variable and not the cause of reduced sleep.

Furthermore, Wei and Williams (2004) examined the relationship between peer victimization and adjustment among junior secondary school students assessing meditation effects, attentive behaviour, anxiety level, conduct problems and academic achievement. Using the McGhee and Mangrum inventory, attention and academic problems; hyperactivity and impulsivity as well as anxiety and oppositional behaviour were measured. The result obtained showed that adjustment incorporates aspects of well being as well as academic achievement.

Methodology

The ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population comprises of all public senior secondary school students in Calabar Municipal and Calabar South Local Government Areas of Cross River State. The stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting a total of seven hundred (700) subjects (364 males and 336 females) from public secondary schools in Calabar Metropolis for the study. A total of 129 of the subjects are between ages 11 -13 years while 422 are between the ages of 14 – 16 years and 149 of them are between 17 – 19 years of age. The instrument used for data collection was a well-structured questionnaire captioned “Mood Disorder and Social Adjustment Questionnaire” (MDSAQ).

The instrument had three sections, Section A contain demographic information of respondents such as age and sex. Section B was a 20 items which measures mood disorder and Section C was a 10 items measuring social adjustment.

The validity of the instrument was determined by two experts in Educational Psychology and one Measurement expert all from Department of Educational Foundations, University of Calabar. The internal consistency of the instrument was established using 30 SS 1 public secondary school students in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area that was not part of the sample. The copies of the instruments distributed were collected, scored and analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability method to obtain the reliability coefficient of the variables in the instrument. The reliability coefficient obtained for the instrument ranged from .70 to .85 which is high enough to justify that the instrument is reliable and should be used for data collection for the study. Data collection was done by the researchers and three research assistants. Copies of the instrument were administered to SS 1 and SS 2 students selected for the study and all the copies were retrieved from the subjects after the exercise. The copies of the instruments collected were analyzed using population t-test and Multiple Linear Regression analysis tested at .05 level of significance.

Presentation of results

Hypothesis one

The hypothesis states that mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is not significantly high.

For the students' mood disorder to be significant, the mean score on their mood disorder should be significantly greater than the reference mean of 50 (the midpoint between, which is 2.5 multiply by 20, the number of items measuring mood disorder). This hypothesis was analyzed using one sample mean (population t-test) analysis tested at .05 level of significance. The result is presented into Table 1.

Table 1
Population t-test analysis of mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis (N=700)

Variable	\bar{x}	Standard deviation	Mean difference	t-value	Sig. of t
Mood disorder	51.560	8.971	1.560	4.601*	.000

*Significant at .05, $p < .05$; $df=699$. Critical $t = 1.966$.

The result of the analysis in Table 1 revealed that the obtained mean score for mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is 51.560 with standard deviation of 8.971 is greater than the reference mean of 50.

The mean difference is statistically significant since the calculated t-value of 4.601 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.966 at .05 level of significance with p-value of .000 and 699 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is not significantly high was rejected since the mean difference between the obtained mean and population or hypothesized mean for mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is statistically significant. Hence, mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is significantly high.

Hypothesis two

Mood disorder does not significantly predict social adjustment among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The independent (predictor) variable is mood disorder while the dependent (criterion) variable is social adjustment among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The hypothesis was analyzed using Linear Regression analysis and the result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Regression analysis of the prediction of social adjustment of secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis with mood disorder

Source of variance	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F-ratio	Sig. of F
Regression	946.604	1	946.604	42.709*	.000
Residual	154703573	698	22.164		
Total	16417.177	699			

Variables	B	Standard error	Beta wts.	t-ratio	p-level
Constant	32.294	1.039		31.089	.000
Mood disorder	-.130	.020	-.240	-6.535*	.000

*Significant at .05 level; R = .240; R-square = .058, Adjusted R-square = .056.

The result in Table 2 shows that the multiple regression analysis produced an F-ratio of 42.709 and p-values of .000, which is statistically significant at .05 level of significance. This result indicates that mood disorder significantly influence social adjustment among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. Mood disorder also produced a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of .240 with a multiple R-square (R^2) of .058 and adjusted multiple R-square (R^2) of .056. The adjusted multiple R-square (R^2) of .056 implies that mood disorder accounted for 5.6 percent (5.8%) of the variance in adjustment among students in Calabar Metropolis.

The result in Table 2 further revealed that the standardised regression beta weights (β) of -.240 was obtained for mood disorder with a t-value of -6.535 and this is significant in predicting social adjustment among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

This means that the higher mood disorder the lower the social adjustment among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The result finally revealed that the unstandardized coefficients (B) of $-.130$ obtained implies that for any unit of mood disorder increases, students social adjustment will reduce by $.13$ percent.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis in hypothesis one revealed that mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is significantly high. This is not surprising because of the rate of misconduct noticed recently among secondary school students especially within Calabar Metropolis where students are being found with difficulty remembering details, making decisions or concentrating as a result of loss of interest in activities that were pleasurable in the past, feelings of hopelessness, restlessness, worthlessness, guilt and so on. The finding of this study is in accordance with Latch (2015) who sees mood disorder as selflessness of personal weakness, character flaws and poor parenting style and this is also in consensus with Krans (2015) who stated that mood disorder is characterized by periods of depression, sometimes alternating with periods of elevated mood. These disorders are associated with imbalances in chemicals that carry signals between brain cells.

The finding of this study is also in line with the study by Allen and Badcock (2003) which indicated that depression is a psychic hibernation that it slows down, defuses aggression and restrains risk taking. The finding of this study is also in agreement with the study by Adewuya and Ologun (2005) which revealed that mood swings results from certain factors which includes depressive symptoms, adolescents' perceptions of family functioning, drug and substance abuse, inferiority complex and so on. The finding is also in accordance with the study by Ugodulunwa and Anakwe (2012) which described social adjustment as a way in which an individual tries to deal with stress, conflict, tension and meet his or her needs while making efforts at the same time to maintain harmonious relationships with the environment.

The finding of this study also concur with the study by Darvern (2004) which examined the relationship between depression and adjustment among third grade high school students and found out that students suffering from depression often experience social difficulties and problems maintaining friendship as a result of mood swings and their tendency to perceive relationships and interactions negatively.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the data analyses, it was concluded that the extent of mood disorder among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is significantly high and this high mood disorder has resulted in poor adjustment among the students. It was also concluded that mood disorders is part of the major crisis that occurs in adolescence stage of life and

proceeds to adulthood which indicated that the more students' exhibit mood disorder the less socially adjusted they become.

It was recommended that teachers should provide an approachable and interactive social climate between themselves and the students to enhance adequate social adjustment. Schools in Calabar Municipality should encourage proper counselling of victims with mood disorder so as to reduce the high rate of poor adjustment among the students. Parents' should also create more positive mutual social atmosphere in the home to prevent mood disorder and enhance proper social adjustment of their ward. Early treatment and identification of victims is important so as to reduce the adverse effect of mood disorder. Policy makers should include workshops to train teachers on how to identify and help students with mood disorders and adjustment problems.

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